

**"PARADIGM SHIFT TOWARDS TRANSDISCIPLINARY ,
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEACHING-LEARNING
IN MANAGEMENT"**

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Abstract :

Educational evolution is a professional responsibility of teaching staff arising from a commitment to understand the effects of teaching on students and to enhance students knowledge and 21st century skill sets as per the industry expectations. In this scenario the new education system under NEP will encourage to reframe the curriculum content as exploratory, interactive ,experiential as well as collaborative learning by giving emphasis on quality in higher education . Rendering effective Teaching is important as it helps students in building their career in a perfect manner as expected and required. As management teaching is a profession, where ideas, principles and knowledge are imparted to students, in a most practical way as needed to fit in to the industry and to lead a successful corporate career. This paper focuses on the modern innovative skills and its impact in achieving excellence in business education.

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Introduction :

Management Education :

Management education is an academic discipline by which students are trained to become a manager, entrepreneurs, business leaders and university professors in business education. In today's competitive business environment, business changes so fast and makes difficult for an organisation to survive the growing competition. With this there is a need of management schools has become very important to impart the relevant management education to students.

Management education should sync with the industries this will help to know the requirements of the industries and also what industries are looking forward from students can be identified. This act as a bridge to fulfill gap between industry and academics, helps to develop the career of students in a particular area.

Importance of Management Education :

- To survive the growing competition, organisation need people with management knowledge.
- All organisation depends upon group effort, group action and team work, management is required, whenever two or more people work together to achieve common objective.

- Management creates team work spirit and co-ordination among specialized effort.
- Efficient and competent managerial leaders alone can convert disorganised resource like men, money, machinery and materials into a productive enterprise.
- It is required for planning, organising, directing, and controlling group efforts.

Current Scenario of Teaching and Learning :

- Teaching is the only theoretical and there is no particle exposure.
- Teaching is strictly restricted to what is in syllabus.
- The syllabus itself is too old or out-dated and steps have not been taken to change.
- As result of above statements the thinking and analysing power has come down among students.
- Race in getting high marks rather on knowledge.
- The interaction between students and teachers is becoming less day by day.

Significance of Innovative Teaching in Management Education:

- Students' achievement and development is possible.
- Students will understand the subject from various angles and get better result in their academics.
- Encourages teachers to use innovative teaching methods to make effective teaching.
- Intense preparation of teachers towards subject is possible.
- Enhance the knowledge of students as well as teachers.
- Helps teachers understand the students attitude and behaviour.

Role of Innovative Teaching Skills for Academic Excellence :

- Sustainability.
- Career development.
- To meet the industrial needs.
- Result oriented approach to the education.
- Social relevance.
- Equity.
- To have a knowledge of the subjects and concepts.

List of 20th Century Teaching Skills :

Most Modern and efficient teaching methods as per new education system includes Case studies, Group discussions, Team assignments, Power point presentation, Filed investigations, role playing, Open textbook study, Committee projects—small groups, Individual projects, Brainstorming, Use of technology and instructional resources, Lecture Practices, Thoughtful Questions, Reflective Responses to Learner Contributions, Rewarding Learner , Active Learning Strategies etc.

Why NEP in Management Education?

- To increase quality in teaching for achieving excellence in management (business) education:
- To identify and adopt effective teaching methods by providing adequate infrastructure and teaching aids.
- To identify the area of interest in students and provide a channel to widen their interest.
- To maintain and improve the standards of teaching.
- To teach the skills required for their career development.
- To identify the careers of students.
- To interact with industry and know the requirements of the industries.

Outcomes of Innovative Teaching Techniques in Management :

- Improves teaching quality of teachers and learning quality of students.
- Students get practical exposure about topics.
- Bothe teachers and students enjoy their learning.
- Always involved in new search of ideas and methods.
- Improves problem solving skills, communication skills, analytical thinking etc.,
- Holistic development of student in all the aspects.
- Industry gets good assets.
- University and colleges enjoys positive result. Universities engage in continues research and development.

Need of the Study :

The purpose of this study is to know the best teaching methods can be adopted in Management education & its impact on student's career development. Teaching methods are most important edge to teachers in the highly competitive environment, where the colleges are striving hard to sustain in the market with quality education, organisational branding and students' development both in professional and personal life. Hence the study focuses on the requirements and expectations from both the teachers as well as from the students under new education system.

Objectives of the Study :

1. To know the effectiveness of new teaching methods in helping students for career development.
2. To identify the strategies to implement the new teaching methods in management education..
3. To identify the teaching aids for management education under NEP.
4. To offer summary, finding and recommendation to the study.

Research Methodology

The Research method adopted is descriptive and survey based method is followed to collect the data .

Sampling Design :

Sampling Method adopted is Convenient sampling method. Sampling frame selected is Bangalore university campus

(MBA programme). Sampling Size for the purpose of the study is 100 students pursuing MBA degree in Bangalore university campus.

Tools for Data Collection :

Primary Data collected through direct interviews and by issuing questionnaire. Secondary Data is obtained through different websites, books and journals.

Plan of Analysis :

From the primary data (by issuing questionnaire and collecting & coding the data collected) analysis and interpretations are done through tables and graphs and inferences are drawn on the basis of the responses of the respondents.

Graphical Representation of the Data Collected :

- Whether there is a positive impact on student's future and career development with the new Teaching Techniques in management education;

- Teaching methods adopted to teach management education under New education policy;

3. Types of approaches effective for management education;

4. Types of learning and its impact on students career growth;

5. Whether NEP Curriculum upholds the Social and Environmental values

6. NEP curriculum Identify the Ability of Students for their Career Development

7. **Different ways the Students get Impact on their Performance and Career Development by Adopting New Teaching Methods under NEP.**

8. **Impact on Student's Performance and Career Development in the Future with the New Teaching Methods**

Findings from the study :

- New teaching techniques Improves teaching quality of teachers and learning quality of students.
- Students get practical exposure about topics.
- Bothe teachers and students enjoy their learning.
- Improves problem solving skills, communication skills, analytical thinking etc.,

- Holistic development of student in all the aspects.
- Industry gets good assets.
- University and colleges enjoys positive result.
- Universities engage in continues research and development.

Suggestions and Recommendations:

- Teachers can adopt interactive sessions, role playing, in basket exercise, business simulations, group discussions, video clippings, guest lecturers from industry, sharing of real time experience and corporate visits etc., as a teaching method other than normal practice to improve the student's learning and career development.
- Teachers must give particle assignments continuously such as filed study, PowerPoint presentations on current affairs, solving case studies, , giving opportunities for students to conduct seminars, workshops, social programmes to enhance the skill sets of students.
- College must appoint a creative person for helping teachers in the preparation of the creative co curriculum and designing the topics in meaningful way.
- Also must appoint technical person to guide teachers in digital mode of teaching.
- The faculty members should understand the significance of effective teaching methods and follow the same in the college.
- The teachers should understand the different approaches to guide a student in the college.
- The teacher fraternity should make students to learn various learning techniques like problem based learning, experimental learning and more integrated learning .
- The teacher's motto in college should always uphold to imbibe social and environmental value system among the student's fraternity.
- The teachers should understand that the management programme bridges gap between the expected skills set in the job market and actually provided in the college and take action to fill the gap.
- The teachers should focus on all the factors like application of technology, preparedness for the same, understanding environment, ambience, new methods, expectations of students and keeping in mind students attendance in the class.
- Students must act in 3 C's creativity, critical thinking and courtesy in college as well as in corporate.
- Students should more logic, rational, ethical and moral.
- Students must bring new ideas to class and must cooperate with teacher if any new thing is teaching in the class.

Conclusion :

From the study we can conclude that the effectiveness of innovative teaching methods is possible when there is a support and willingness from colleges and cooperation from students in the application of new innovative teaching methods. These teaching methods will not only help faculty members but also students and college at large. Students will be properly trained up before taking up the aspired job in job market. And at the same time the colleges get

benefited with the quality enhancement and development, it creates a brand in the eyes of the society; in turn the good quality colleges will build a good educated society. A true learning happens in all the ways be it for faculty members, students and colleges as whole.

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